
A COMPREHENSIVE STUDY ON IMPACT OF JUNK FOOD ON MENTAL HEALTH OF YOUTH

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ABSTRACT

The consumption of ultra-processed foods has been linked to a rise in chronic diseases such as hypertension, clinical depression, anxiety disorders, and bipolar disorder. These foods are designed to be tasty and addictive, leading to increased cravings and consumption. The data collected are from a secondary source which are collected from various journals and published papers. Despite their detrimental effects on health and mental aspects, processed foods have become synonymous with celebration in our culture, contributing to the proliferation of unhealthy eating habits. This research aims to explore the impact of junk and processed foods on the mental health of young individuals, highlighting the role of processed ingredients in causing inflammation in the body and brain, which may contribute to mood disorders, including anxiety and depression.

Keywords: Processed Food, Junk Food, Eating Habits, Mental Health, Youths.

I. INTRODUCTION

Even during our deep sleep our minds will still be functioning, even though it weighs 2% of our body mass but still it consumes 20% of the calories we consume for our daily need to maintain some functions of our body like balancing temperature, breath rate, heart rate and controlling of emotions. With this we can understand the importance of brain work which is indirectly reflecting and relating to the food we consume [1]. The brain functions best when we feed with all the required nutrients and antioxidants which nourishes and enhances our body and mind. The processed foods like packed snacks, bread, bun etc, can disrupt the production of certain hormones which produces happiness. Inflammation in the body is increasing in the youth due to the consumption of poor quality and unhealthy foods and many scientific studies have proven that these are some of the main reasons for increased risk of depression [2].

II. RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

1. To provide a comprehensive overview of the junk food industry.
2. To assess the impact of junk food consumption on health across various sectors through a literature review.
3. To identify and analyze the top nations with the highest expenditure on junk food consumption among youth.
4. To examine the consumption rates of junk food in different states of India.
5. To explore alternative options to traditional junk food products and suggest strategies to mitigate their negative impact on health.

III. METHODOLOGY

This paper mainly focuses on assessing the expenditure of youths on junk food globally and finds alternatives for these junk foods and highlights the effects of junk food on mental health. This study is completely based on secondary data and the data collected from various journals and referred various case study papers.

IV. RELATED RESEARCH WORK

These are some of the similar works and papers which are concentrated on the impacts of junk food in different sectors of their choices.

Table 1: Related contributions given by different authors.

Sl.No	Area of Study	Focus	Reference
1	Impact of Junk food on Physical and Mental health of the Youngsters.	Find out the frequency of consumption of Junk food preparation and their effects on Physical & Mental health in the youngsters of Bhopal city with special reference to Viruddha Ahara.	Verma, R., Bansal, C., & Jain, T. (2020).[3]
2	Association between university student junk food consumption and mental health.	Determine the relationship between university students' consumption of junk food and their levels of stress, anxiety, and depression.	ElBarazi, A., & Tikamdas, R. (2023).[4]
3	Junk food consumption and psychological distress in children and adolescents.	This study aimed to conduct a meta-analysis to clarify the association between junk food consumption and psychological distress in children and adolescents.	Malmir, H., et al. (2023).[5]
4	Consumption of sugar-sweetened beverages and fast foods deteriorates adolescents' mental health	Sugar-sweetened beverage (SSB) and fast-food consumption is significantly associated with adolescents' poor mental health. Furthermore, sugar-sweetened beverage and fast-food consumption might form clustered diet patterns with significant positive associations in adolescent high school students.	Ra, J. S. (2022). [6]
5	Effect of junk food consumption on the nutritional status of adolescents.	Junk food consumption affects adolescent brain development in a manner that restricts their capacity for thought, learning, and memory. Additionally, it might make it harder to control impulsive behavior, and it might potentially raise an adolescent's likelihood of anxiety and depression.	Mahjabin, A. (2023).[7]
6	Effects of junk food over adolescent's health	The present study aims to find out the effects of junk food and adolescent's health among Cuddalore district of Tamilnadu. Junk foods are rich in calories, salt and fats. Excess consumption of junk foods leads rise to wide variety of health disorders. School canteens are offering foods high in fat and sugar which actually contributing to the youth weight gain along with other problems like infections, food poisonings and dental diseases.	Jothilakshmi, M.(2018).[8]

7	Impact of junk food advertisement on health of teenagers.	To study the impact of junk food advertisement on teenagers habits.	Sheena, J. D., & Haryana, B. R. (2020). [9]
8	Association of perceived stress with healthy and unhealthy food consumption among teenagers.	To evaluate unhealthy and healthy food consumption and their association with perceived stress in teenagers.	Tariq, S., Tariq, S., & Tariq, S. (2019). [10]

V. TOP NATIONS WHICH ARE SPENDING HIGH ON CONSUMPTION OF JUNK FOOD AMONG YOUTHS

Here is the list of top 10 nations which are using highest junk foods and are prone to get affected with different mental and physical health [11].

Figure 1: Top 10 nations which are in high consumption of junk food.

The above graph represents the nations which are spending highest money on consumption of junk and ultra processed food, in this U.S.A is the leading nation to consume more junk foods in the world. In the above graph we can see U.S.A. In a year, one person spends nearly \$1,200 on frozen foods in America, the Average Americans spend \$70,000 in their lifetime, on a day 50 million Americans consume fast food. So the global fast food market is estimated to be worth 931.7 billion dollars. Around 34% of adolescents consume fast food [12]

VI. STUDY OF STATES WHICH ARE HAVING HIGHEST CONSUMPTION OF JUNK FOOD IN INDIA

According to NFHS-5(National Family Health Survey) nearly 80% men and women in Mizoram consumes more fried foods and processed products daily. Food consumption is not just becoming an unhealthy lifestyle habit but also a full fledge prediction to access the health problems related to junk foods the burden of the addiction to junk food was conducted in Junk Food Addiction Across Generations in Urban Karnataka, India using addiction scale to describe the alternative diets followed cross sectional study was conducted among the people across three generations and using convenient samplings sample size of 500 wears selected I didn't to the junk food was assist by novel junk food addiction skill develop for the study and all 500 studies subjects had consumed either junk food or fast food any time in the past 1 year but total of 211 subjects reported accurate junk food addiction was observed in more than 1 10th of the subjects majority had milled addiction and observed equally between millennial and generation z obesity habits and gadgets had independent effects on junk food addiction [17].

The index ranks states on five parameters of food safety; Human resources and institutional data, compliance, food testing facility, training and capacity building besides consumer empowerment. Gujarat, Kerala and Tamil Nadu have topped an index that ranks states on food safety parameters for the year 2020-21 [13].

VII. IMPACTS OF JUNK FOODS ON MENTAL HEALTH

Sugar processed foods and junk foods are harmful for both mental as well as physical health for the humans. The oils are being reused for preparation of fried foods that are available at cheap costs due to reduce the

production costs, this leads to various effects and have a chance of reduction in the life expectancy of humans and more processed foods are supplied in plastic which in turn are again harmful and creates more problems for society.

There are several reasons to say that junk food is very much harmful for human health, these foods can transmit negative signals into our brain and this increases several mental issues.

1. Memory Problems: Junk Food is high in hydrogenated fatty acid and sugar which can curb the memory and learning. This has been noticed among children who consume carbonated drinks regularly and addicted to street foods are likely to lose memory and impact negatively on their physical health.

2. Depression: some processed food which are consumed in excess can bring noticeable changes in neurotransmitters of your body and it results in creating a deep craving all the time whenever you feel low, these foods also affect your neurotransmitters like dopamine and serotonin, which leads to depression and various mental disorders.

3. Irritability: It is important to have patience in every human being and it is such a weapon which could bring numerous changes to one's life, but if we lose this character we will end up in a negative and pessimistic situation. Canadian researchers have found that food has a direct impact on our mental stability and conscious, so the result of fast food has created an impatient behaviour among the people which is a negative impact on our social life.

4. Fructose effects on mental health: The hypothalamus plays a crucial role in the brain by keeping the body in a stable state. So we should avoid the junk foods and processed foods as much as possible. According to various study done by Cassie Bjork, Founder of Healthy Simple Life says sugar can be more addictive than cocaine.

5. Anxiety: Frozen food eating patterns are closely having a link to feelings and stress. Foods high in saturated fats, Tran's fats and omega-6 fatty acids can cause inflammation; on the other hand, refined carbohydrates can lead to imbalance in sugar, blood levels and also causes various anxious issues.

6. Hyperactivity: Sodium Benzoate generally recognizes to be safe if it is used in an appropriate way i.e., 0.1% which is considered to be safe, but due to several businesses profits and other factors people are not using in a given manner which is resulting in severe mood swings among young generations.

7. Risk of Dementia: when there is an imbalance in the proper diet of a person for several years it may start reacting in a negative form by causing such diseases. This may occur due to aging but there are chances and cases where brain injury, diabetes are being one of the major reasons.

8. Lowers Self Control: Trans fats in processed foods which can prevent your brain from understanding the limits, this results in lessened self-control. Those who consume processed food are more likely to eat more. Several studies have shown this to be true. In one particular study, caloric intake increased by approximately 500 calories a day in the group following an ultra-processed food diet [14].

VIII. ANALYZE THE ALTERNATIVES FOR THE JUNKS

The junk food is having so many effects on mental and physical health; there are several alternatives for these processed foods and they are;

1. Kale chips as an alternative to potato chips. Crispy and nutrient-dense, kale chips will quell your want for salt. All you have to do is toss the kale leaves with olive oil and your preferred seasonings then bake them until crispy. Nutrient-dense, high in calcium, vitamin C, and vitamin K, kale chips are low in calories.

2. Consider dried fruit in place of candies. Sweet and chewy, dried fruit is a great source of vitamins, minerals, and fibre. To eliminate additional sugar, opt for unsweetened varieties. Dried figs, mangoes, and apricots are a few delectable possibilities.

3. Opt for frozen yogurt instead of ice cream. An excellent and creamy substitute for ice cream is frozen yogurt. Compared to conventional ice cream, it contains less fat and calories.

4. Try sparkling water in instead of soda. Another bubbly and delicious option to soda is sparkling water. Because it doesn't include artificial sweeteners or added sugar, it's a healthy option for slake your thirst. For taste, you can add a squeeze of lemon or lime juice or a splash of fruit juice.

5. Try making homemade granola bars in place of cookies. A delicious and filling snack that's simple to make at home are granola bars. Combine oats, peanut butter, nuts, seeds, and dried fruit with a small amount of honey and bake till golden brown. High in fibre and protein, homemade granola bars are free of artificial additives and preservatives [15].

IX. THE DISTRIBUTION OF COMMONLY CONSUMED FAST/JUNK FOOD

Depression, memory loss, and cognitive decline are among the mental health issues that are thought to be influenced by chronic inflammation, both in their early stages and as they worsen.

Figure 2: Percentage of Junk Food Consumed by College Students

In the above figure we can see that the college students are more addicted to chocolates and soft drinks which are increasing the memory loss cases and also deteriorating the creative minds of youths [16].

X. FINDINGS

The findings show that ultra-processed foods have a significant negative impact on the mental and physical health of youth, potentially affecting their creativity. To address this issue, prioritizing education campaigns promoting healthy eating habits is crucial to raise awareness among younger generations about the consequences and encourage healthier choices, ultimately saving lives and future generations.

XI. SUGGESTIONS

1. In the recent years it is observed that nations like U.S.A and Canada are using more of these processed and junk foods which has to be reduced, and they have switch towards healthy food consumption for better life.
2. In the above study it is observed that Mizoram state in India is being affected more in terms of processed food around 80% of its population. This could be reduced by including many substitutes which are being way healthier.
3. The impact of the junk food is a serious issue and it is being mainly affected on youths of the nation this will be a greater impact to the future of the nation.
4. The recent studies in Uttar Kannada district of Karnataka it was found that Millennial and generation Z are the most being affected due to the consumption of junk food.

XII. CONCLUSION

It's better to enjoy the food that is made healthier and which are necessary to improve our mental and physical health, because this is a long-lasting asset for any human being until their death, maybe having junk food once a while is ok but shouldn't be a regular diet.

XIII. REFERENCES

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